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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

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акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

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дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

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Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxamatkulovich

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YUSUPOV Adkham Ulugbekovich

PhD student

KILICHEV Ibodulla Abdullayevich

DSc, professor

Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

**STUDY OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRANSCRANIAL MAGNETIC STIMULATION
IN THE TREATMENT OF MOTOR APHASIA AFTER ISCHEMIC STROKE***Corresponding author: Yusupov U. Adkham, adham.yusupov.95@mail.ru*

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10895986>**ABSTRACT**

Post-stroke aphasia is one of the main concerns of patients and their relatives. At the same time, effective methods for the treatment of patients with motor aphasia have not yet been created. That is why it is important to know aphasias and learn how to effectively treat them. In this article, transcranial magnetic stimulation and pharmacological treatment in the treatment of motor aphasia were compared with a control group.

Keywords: stroke, aphasia, treatment, transcranial magnetic stimulation, memantine.

ЮСУПОВ Адхам Улугбекович

PhD студент

КИЛИЧЕВ Ибодулла Абдуллаевич

Д.м.н., профессор

Ургенчский филиал Ташкентской Медицинской Академии

**ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ТРАНСКРАНИАЛЬНОЙ МАГНИТНОЙ
СТИМУЛЯЦИИ ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ МОТОРНОЙ АФАЗИИ ПОСЛЕ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОГО
ИНСУЛЬТА****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Постинсультная афазия является одной из основных проблем пациентов и их родственников. В то же время эффективные методы лечения больных моторной афазией до сих пор не созданы. Вот почему важно знать афазии и научиться эффективно их лечить. В этой статье транскраниальная магнитная стимуляция и фармакологическое лечение при лечении моторной афазии сравнивались с контрольной группой.

Ключевые слова: инсульт, афазия, лечение, транскраниальная магнитная стимуляция, мемантин.

YUSUPOV Adham Ulug'bekovich

Mustaqil izlanuvchi

KILICHEV Ibodulla Abdullayevich

t.f.d., professor

Toshkent Tibbiyot Akademiyasi Urganch filiali

ISHEMIK INSULTDAN KEYINGI MOTOR AFAZIYANI DAVOLASHDA TRANSKRANIAL MAGNITLI STIMULYATSIYA VA MEMANTIN PREPARATINING SAMARADORLIGINI O'RGANISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Insultdan keyingi afaziya bemorlar va ularning yaqinlarini tashvishga soladigan asosiy muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, motor afaziyali bemorlarni davolash bo'yicha samarali usullar haligacha yaratilmagan. Shu sababli afaziyalarni bilish va ularni samarali davolash usullarini o'rganish muhimdir. Mazkur maqolada motor afaziyani davolashda transkraniyal magnitli stimulyatsiya va farmakologik davo nazorat guruhi bilan qiyosiy tahlil qilib o'rganildi

Kalit so'zlar: Insult, afaziya, davolash, transkraniyal magnitli stimulyatsiya, memantin.

Kirish: Hozirgi kunda insult nogironlik va o'limga olib keladigan asosiy kasalliklardan biridir [1]. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, hozirda AQShda 2 millionga yaqin odam afaziya bilan yashaydi. Har yili qo'shimcha 180 000 ta yangi holat aniqlanadi [18]. Insultga uchragan 65 yoshgacha bo'lgan odamlarning taxminan 15 foizida afaziya rivojlanadi. 85 yoshdan oshgan odamlarning qariyb 45 foizida insultdan keyingi afaziya rivojlanadi [19]. Ritmik transkraniyal magnitli stimulyatsiya (rTMS) ko'plab tadqiqotlarda insultning falajlik, disfagiya, dizartriya, og'riq, tutqanoq va afaziya kabi asoratlarini davolash uchun yangicha yondashuv sifatida ishlatilgan [2-10]. Insult bilan kasallangan bemorlarning taxminan 15-40% da nutq muammolar, shu jumladan duduqlanish, so'z topishga qiynalish, agrammatik nutq mavjud [11]. Milliy afaziya assotsiatsiyasining tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, afaziya mushaklar distrofiyasi va Parkinson kasalligidan ko'ra ko'proq tarqalgan.

Nutq markazlariga bosh miya chap yarimsharidagi Brok va Vernik sohalari, miyaning o'ng yarimsharidagi gomologik sohalari, peshona bo'lagining prefrontal va premotor sohalari va tepa bo'lagining pastki qismi kiradi [12,13]. Bir qancha bemorlarda insultning turli davrlarida bosh miya po'stlog'ining ikki tomonlama faollashuvi pozitron emission tomografiyasi, funktsional magnit rezonans tomografiyasi yordamida tekshirilganda aniqlangan [14]. Ko'plab tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, past chastotali rTMS bosh miyaning zararlanmagan yarimsharida qo'llanilganida bemorlarda nutq tiklanishi samarali bo'lishi mumkin [10]. Shuningdek, shikastlangan yarimsharda yuqori chastotali rTMS qo'llanilganida ham ijobiy natijalar qayd etilgan [10,15].

Afaziya bilan kasallangan bemorlar o'z istaklari va ehtiyojlarini yetkazishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Afaziya bilan kasallangan ba'zi bemorlar o'zlarining holatini yaxshi tushunishadi, bu esa ularda og'ir depressiyaga olib kelishi mumkin.

Tanskraniyal magnitli stimulyatsiya (TMS) miya bo'ylab magnit maydonini keltirib chiqaradigan, o'zidan qisqa, intensiv to'lqinlar ajratib turuvchi qurulma hisoblanadi [16]. TMS elektromagnit induksiya qonuniga asoslangan bo'lib, subyektning boshiga o'rnatilgan uskuna orqali o'tadigan elektr tokining impulsi tez o'zgaruvchan magnit impuls hosil qiladi, u bosh terisi va bosh suyagidan o'tib po'stloqqa yetib boradi. Magnit maydon pulsi, o'z navbatida, miyada po'stloq neyronlarida harakat potentsiallarini qo'zg'atadi [17]. Ritmik TMS po'stloq depolyarizatsiyasini keltirib chiqaradi va bosh miyada neyropastik o'zgarishlarni keltirib chiqaradi. TMS xavfsiz davo usuli bo'lsada, ba'zan rTMS tutqanoq xurujlarini keltirib chiqarishi mumkin va miyaning fokal zararlanishlari, neyrodegenerativ kasalliklar, elektron implantlar, yurak stimulyatori bo'lgan va antidepressantlar kabi tutqanoq bo'shasini pasaytiradigan preparatlarni qabul qiladigan bemorlarda ehtiyot bo'lish kerak [16].

Material va usullar: Tadqiqot uchun ishemik insultdan keyin rivojlargan motor afaziyasi mavjud 60 ta bemor ajratilib olindi. Bemorlar randomizatsiyalangan uchta guruhga bo'lindi: TMS qo'llanilgan (20 ta bemor), farmokalogik davo oluvchi (21 ta bemor) va nazorat (19 ta bemor) guruh.

Birinchi guruh bemorlarga 10 kun davomida bosh miya o'ng yarimshari markaz oldi pushtasi bo'ylab rTMS qo'llanildi. Brok markazi neyronavigatsiya protokoli bo'yicha aniqlab olindi. TMS parametrlari quyidagicha belgilandi: davomiyligi- 30 minut, chastotasi 1 Gts, puls soni- 600 ta, stimulyatsiya va pauza nisbati 30:5 sekund, motor qo'zg'alish chegarasi – «5»lik qoidasi bo'yicha aniqlandi. Tinchlikdagi motor bo'sag'a potentsiali har bir bemorda o'ng birlamchi harakat zonasida (gr. precentralis) aniqlab olindi.

Ikkinchi guruh bemorlarga keng qo'llaniladigan preparat- Memantin 10mg quyidagi sxema bo'yicha buyurildi: 5 mg ertalab 7 kun keyin, 10 mg ertalab 7 kun keyin, 15 mg ertalab 45 kun.

Nazorat guruh bemorlarida bosh miya yarimsharlari orasiga-verteks tinchlikdagi motor bo'sag'a potentsialining 10% miqdori bilan TMS qo'llanildi. Bemorlarda klinik samara davolash kursi tugagach shu zahoti va 2 oydan keyin Western Battery shkalasi orqali baholab borildi.

Tadqiqot 2022-2023-yil vaqt oralig'ida «Umid shifokor» xususiy klinikasi, Respublika shoshilinch tibbiy yordam tibbiyot markazi Xorazm filiali va Xorazm viloyati ko'p tarmoqli tibbiyot markazida olib borildi.

Tadqiqot uchun bosh miya chap o'rta arteriyasi havzasi bo'ylab ishemik insult o'tqazgan 38-75 yosh chegarasidagi 24 ta ayol va 36 ta erkak bemorlar olindi. Barcha bemorlar insultning erta va kechki tiklanish davridagi bemorlar hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot uchun TMSga qarshi ko'rsatma mavjud bemorlar, chapaqaylar va insultning o'tkir va qoldiq asoratlar davridagi bemorlar olinmadi.

Bemorlarning 28 tasida muolaja davomida bosh og'rishi, paresteziya, bosh aylanishi, 1ta bemorda sinkopal holat kuzatildi. Statistik tahlil SPSS-24.0 (IBM Corp) dasturi orqali amalga oshirildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Bemorlarning nutqi davolashning so'ngi kunida Western Battery shkalasi orqali baholanganda uchala guruh bemorlarning nutqida sezilarli farq aniqlanmadi (jadval 1). Bemorlar ikki oydan keyin qayta baholanganda guruhlar orasida narsalar nomini topish ($p=0.1$) va eshitib tushunish ($p=0.2$) kabi nutq komponentlarida sezilarli farqlar aniqlandi. rTMS olgan bemorlarning narsalar nomini topish borasidagi shkala ballari farmokalogik davo olgan va nazorat guruhiga nisbatan ($p=0.5$) katta farqni ko'rsatdi.

Jadval 1

Bemorlarning demografik ko'rsatkichlari va davolashni boshlashdan oldingi Western Battery shkalasi bo'yicha to'plagan o'rtacha ballari

	Farmokalogik	rTMS	Nazorat
Soni	21	20	19
Erkak: Ayol	13:8	11:9	12:7
Yoshi, o'rtacha (SD)	66.7 (10.3)	65.6 (9.6)	67.3 (10.9)
Erkin nutq, o'rtacha (SD)	10.2 (6.3)	11.4 (5.8)	10.8 (5.6)
Eshitib tushinish, o'rtacha (SD)	54.4 (27.6)	55.6 (25.8)	56.3 (23.4)
So'zlarni takrorlay olish, o'rtacha (SD)	50.6 (26.4)	54.6 (27.2)	52.7 (23.9)
Narsalar nomini topish, o'rtacha (SD)	44.5 (21.3)	43.6 (20.6)	46.1 (21.8)
O'qib tushunish, o'rtacha (SD)	32.2 (16.2)	33.5 (15.4)	30.3 (14.7)
Aytilgan so'zni yoza olish, o'rtacha (SD)	3.2 (1.1)	3.2 (1.2)	2.8 (1.3)

Memantin qabul qilgan bemorlarda shkalaning eshitib tushunish bandidagi ballari TMS olgan bemorlarga qaraganda ($p=0.5$) sezilarli yaxshilandi (jadval 2). Hech qaysi guruhda narsalar nomini topa olish va gaplarni tushunish ballarida korrelyatsiya aniqlanmadi. Western Battery

shkalasi ballarining umumiy yig'indisi bo'yicha TMS olgan bemorlar qolgan guruhlarga nisbatan ko'proq ball to'plashdi.

Jadval 2

Uchala guruh bemorlarining davolash tugagandan keyingi va 2 oydan keyingi Western Battery shkalasi bo'yicha umumiy ballarining nisbat tahlili

	Farmokalogik	rTMS	Nazorat
1-kun	0.05 (0.26)	0.00 (0.39)	0.00 (0.28)
60-kun	0.15 (0.46)	0.48 (0.39)	0.65 (1.05)
Erkin nutq			
1-kun	0.92 (0.84)	0.84 (1.92)	1.05 (0.87)
60-kun	2.23 (2.12)	1.52 (2.1)	2.08 (2.06)
Eshitib tushunish			
1-kun	1.07 (1.07)	0.88 (1.02)	0.92 (1.18)
60-kun	1.24 (0.87)	1.20 (0.98)	0.98 (1.19)
So'zlarni takrorlay olish			
1-kun	1.09 (1.19)	0.96 (1.11)	0.88 (0.95)
60-kun	1.56 (0.82)	1.23 (1.12)	1.06 (1.23)
Narsalar nomini topish			
1-kun	1.12 (1.25)	1.03 (1.18)	1.02 (0.95)
60-kun	1.29 (1.06)	1.32 (1.08)	1.22 (1.12)
O'qib tushunish			
1-kun	1.03 (0.95)	0.95 (0.56)	1.05 (0.88)
60-kun	1.21 (0.96)	1.06 (0.680)	1.20 (0.96)
Aytilgan so'zni yoza olish			

Xulosalar: Mazkur tadqiqot TMS va memantin preparatining insultdan keyingi motor afaziya bilan kasallangan bemorlarda qanchalik samarali ekanligini aniqlash maqsadida o'tqazildi. Uchta asosiy natija olindi: (1) rTMS motor afaziya bilan kasallangan bemorlarda anomiyani davolashda yaxshi samarali usul, (2) TMSning samarali ta'siri bemorlarda darhol sezilmaydi, (3) Memantin preparati bemorlarning eshitgan gapini tushunish qobiliyatini yaxshiladi. Past chastotali rTMS Brok sohasi bo'ylab qo'llanilganda qarama-qarshi yarimshardagi shu markazni qo'zg'atishi mumkin va bu keyinchalik bosh miyada boshqa alternativ neyronlararo sinapslar hosil bo'lishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Keyingi tadqiqotlarda bemorlarni insultning qoldiq asoratlar davrida ham baholash TMSning samarasini ko'proq ko'rsatib berishi mumkin.

Zararlanmagan bosh miya po'stlog'i bo'ylab yo'naltirilgan past chastotali TMS xavfsiz davo usulidir. 10 kun davomiylikdagi past chastotali TMS bemorlardagi anomiyani 2 oy ichida sezilarli yaxshilaydi. Memantin preparatini qabul qilgan bemorlarda nazorat guruhi bemorlariga nisbatan tuzalish sezilarli yaxshilanmadi. Bizning natijalarimiz shuni ko'rsdiki, rTMS markaziy nerv sistemasining neyroplastligini oshira oladi.

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Информация об авторах:

Юсупов Адхам Улугбекович- Ассистент кафедры. Ургенчский филиал Ташкентской Медицинской Академии, Ургенч, Узбекистан. E-mail: adham.yusupov.95@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-9675-5419>

Киличев Ибодулла Абдуллаевич- д.м.н., профессор. Ургенчский филиал Ташкентской Медицинской Академии, Ургенч, Узбекистан. E-mail: qlichev@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3219-5539>

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Юсупов А.У. — сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Information about the authors:

Adkham U. Yusupov — PhD student. Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy, Urgench, Uzbekistan; E-mail: adham.yusupov.95@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-9675-5419>

Ibodulla A. Kilichev — DSc, Professor. Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy, Urgench, Uzbekistan; E-mail: qlichev@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3219-5539>

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

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Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000